

Report on the first Delphi study

1. Delphi study plan

The aim of the research

The goal of conducting the Delphi study is to gain a deeper insight into the necessary "soft" skills of young people, in order to, through the proposal of a training program, encourage the development of these skills, which will make it easier for young people to successfully enter the work sphere when hiring or starting their own business. It is based on the assumption that young people acquire the necessary minimum professional knowledge through formal education (the so-called "hard" skills necessary for the successful execution of work tasks defined by the job description), but that the so-called "soft" skills are also very important for successful inclusion in the sphere of work and subsequent career development (Sharvari & Kulkarni, 2019). By "soft" skills in this research is meant a set of interpersonal skills, such as strong communication skills, mentoring skills of colleagues, leadership and team work, negotiation, social and other, but also intrapersonal skills, such as personal qualities, attitudes, motives, forms of behaviour, etc., which enable young people to successfully interact with other subjects in the business sphere, recognize opportunities on the market, as the realization of set goals.

In this sense, the following are the special objectives of the research:

1. Conceptual definition and identification of soft skills of individuals important in modern business conditions,
2. Identifying reasons and approaches to developing soft skills,
3. Selection of soft skills that respondents consider crucial for starting their own business,
4. Selection of soft skills that respondents consider crucial for positive evaluation by the human resource management (HRM) department in the selection process,
5. Identifying ways to recognize/assess soft skills.

Research instrument

The research instrument is the Questionnaire for experts, in the first and second round of research.

Table 1. The first round – the questionnaire for experts for an in-depth interview

Research Objective (RO)	Question
n/a	Introduce yourself and briefly explain your experience in HRM and/or running your own business.
RO 1	1. How would you define soft skills? Accompanying questions: 1a) Is it possible to ignore soft skills in modern business conditions?*
RO 1	2. Is the presence of soft skills more important than hard skills for some jobs?*
RO 3	3. What are the soft skills of individuals desirable in modern business conditions? 2a) If yes, what are the jobs? (set only if the expert said YES)

RO 4	
RO 2	4. What do you think are the reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace?
RO 2	5. According to your opinion and experience, how should the activities of building and strengthening soft skills be approached in the formal education system, and how in the workplace?
RO 2	6. What are the necessary prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals?
RO 3 RO 4	7. What soft skills would you identify as key to starting and successfully running your own business?
RO 3 RO 4	8. Which soft skills would you identify as key for positive evaluation by the HRM service in the selection process?
RO 5	9. Based on your experience, is it difficult to assess/recognize an individual's soft skills? * 9a) In what way is it possible to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals?

* Respondents answer these questions with "YES" and "NO". For other questions, the respondents give at least 5 answers. For these questions, in the process of summarizing the results, the answers "YES" and answers "NO" should be counted. For other questions, all answers given by all respondents should be included in the list of offered answers, in order to create a list of answers.

Sample research

The plan is to conduct a Delphi study with experts in the field of human resource management (HRM), as well as successful entrepreneurs. In this Delphi study 20 experts from mentioned field were participated. Respondents from the field of HRM have significant experience in the process of recruitment and selection of candidates, i.e., in the employment process (and thus also in the assessment of the candidate's "soft" skills). Respondents from the field of entrepreneurship are persons who successfully run their own entrepreneurial ventures (and recruit and select candidates themselves) and are able to convey which "soft" skills are important for success in their business. *Gender:* Respondents are members of both genders.

Resources

For the implementation of the Delphi study, two implementers are foreseen, for each partner: a moderator and an associate who will record the answers and opinions of the respondents, as well as the common conclusions that will be reached.

An in-depth interview can be conducted face-to-face or via telephone or some form of online video streaming communication.

Time

The estimated duration of the conversation with each expert is 15 minutes.

Deadlines

The planned date for the realization of the first round of the Delphi study is from November 6 to 11, 2023. The processing of collected data and the creation of questionnaires for the second round is planned for the period from November 13 to 18, 2023. Data collection by distributing questionnaires in the second round of the Delphi study is planned for the period November 20 to 25, 2023. The questionnaires are sent to the experts who participated in the first round of the Delphi study. The analysis of the collected data and the compilation of the Report on the conducted Delphi study must be completed by November 30, 2023.

2. First round Delphi study results

After receiving the answers given by the respondents, their summarization follows, first at the level of each country, and then at the project level (the coordinators of each partner send summary answers to the questions to the project coordinator, and the coordinator summarizes them at the project level). The summary answers are the basis for creating a questionnaire for experts for the second round of research.

Coordinators by country deliver precisely defined statistics for each of the questions, namely:

1. Percentage of answers YES/NO and that 1st question under a), 2nd and 9th question,
2. Summarized list (5 answers per expert, but in the final list all listed with the number of citations in order to identify the key ones by the number of citations.

1. More than 90% of experts said that it is not possible to ignore soft skills in modern business conditions (question 1a) and that the presence of soft skills is more important than hard skills for some jobs. Also, the same percentage of experts confirmed that it is difficult to assess/recognize an individual's soft skills.

2. The most frequent answers concerning other research questions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Delphi study – answers systematized based on first round of interviews

DELPHI STUDY REPORT	
Research objective (RO)	Questions
RO 1	1. How would you define soft skills? <p style="text-align: center;"> Communication skills Teamwork skills Adaptability Emotional intelligence Empathy </p> Accompanying question: 1a) Is it possible to ignore soft skills in modern business conditions? * No
RO 1	2. Is the presence of soft skills more important than hard skills for some jobs?* Yes 2a) If yes, what are the jobs? (set only if the expert said YES) <p style="text-align: center;"> Human resources Leadership and management Customer service </p>

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	Marketing CEO
RO3 RO4	<p>3. What are the soft skills of individuals desirable in modern business conditions?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Communication skills Adaptability and flexibility Emotional intelligence Teamwork and collaboration Critical thinking </p>
RO2	<p>4. What do you think are the reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Building strong relationships Contribute to teamwork Motivate the staff Opportunity for personal development Conflict resolution </p>
RO2	<p>5. According to your opinion and experience, how should the activities of building and strengthening soft skills be approached in the formal education system, and how in the workplace?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Interview Special courses and training programs Encourage group projects and workshops Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs Assertive communication </p>
RO2	<p>6. What are the necessary prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Openness to learning Empathy Communication Skills Adaptability Self-awareness </p>
RO3 RO4	<p>7. What soft skills would you identify as key to starting and successfully running your own business?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Leadership skills Communication skills Emotional intelligence Problem-solving skills Teamwork </p>
RO3 RO4	<p>8. Which soft skills would you identify as key for positive evaluation by the HRM service in the selection process?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Communication skills Teamwork Adaptability and flexibility Emotional Intelligence Problem solving skills </p>
RO5	<p>9. Based on your experience, is it difficult to assess/recognize an individual's soft</p>

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	<p>skills?* Yes.</p> <p>9a) In what way is it possible to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Psychological tests Interviewing Observation in team activities Reference checks Detailed observation of communication and behavior</p>
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3. Second round Delphi study questionnaire

Based on the analysis of qualitative data obtained in the first round of empirical research, i.e. through in-depth interviews, but also on the basis of a previously prepared systematic literature review, an instrument is developed for the second round of research in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to experts with the aim of reaching agreement on the key soft skills needed either for starting one's own business, or for a positive evaluation by the HRM department in the selection process.

For each question that involves enumerating the answers, the experts declare themselves with grades from 1 to 5, using a Likert scale, whereby the experts are given an explanation of the grades according to the following meaning of the grade:

- 1 – Unnecessary,
- 2 - Completely insignificant,
- 3 – Partially significant,
- 4 – Significantly,
- 5 – Very significant.

Table 3. QUESTIONNAIRE FOR EXPERTS

Dear Sir/Madam, we hereby invite you to participate in the second round of Delphi study. If you have questions related to the research, you can contact the researchers via the email address: useipmproject@gmail.com. Mark the answers that express your opinion about the following statements.

Question	Answer				
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Teamwork skills	1	2	3	4	5
c) Adaptability	1	2	3	4	5
d) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
e) Empathy	1	2	3	4	5
1a) Is it possible to ignore soft skills in modern business conditions?	NO	YES			

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2. Is the presence of soft skills more important than hard skills for some jobs?	NO	YES			
2a) If yes, how significant is it for the following jobs?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Human resources	1	2	3	4	5
b) Leadership and management	1	2	3	4	5
c) Customer service	1	2	3	4	5
d) Marketing	1	2	3	4	5
e) CEO	1	2	3	4	5
3. How important are the following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Adaptability and flexibility	1	2	3	4	5
c) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
d) Team work and cooperation	1	2	3	4	5
e) Critical thinking	1	2	3	4	5
4. How important are the following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Building strong relationships	1	2	3	4	5
b) Contribution to teamwork	1	2	3	4	5
c) Motivating staff	1	2	3	4	5
d) Opportunity for personal development	1	2	3	4	5
e) Resolving conflicts	1	2	3	4	5
5) According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system, and in which of the following ways in the workplace, soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
5.1) In the education system:					
a) Encourage group projects	1	2	3	4	5
b) Special courses and training programs	1	2	3	4	5
c) Encourage workshops	1	2	3	4	5
d) Combination of typical classroom learning/training	1	2	3	4	5

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programs					
e) Assertive communication	1	2	3	4	5
5.2) In the workplace:					
a) Interview	1	2	3	4	5
b) Special courses and training programs	1	2	3	4	5
c) Mentoring one-on-one or in groups	1	2	3	4	5
d) Active communication with employees	1	2	3	4	5
e) Being receptive to feedback	1	2	3	4	5
6. How important are the following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Openness to learning	1	2	3	4	5
b) Empathy	1	2	3	4	5
c) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
d) Adaptability	1	2	3	4	5
e) Self-awareness	1	2	3	4	5
7. To what extent are the following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Leadership skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
c) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
d) Problem solving skills	1	2	3	4	5
e) Teamwork	1	2	3	4	5
8. To what extent are the following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Team work	1	2	3	4	5
c) Adaptability and flexibility	1	2	3	4	5
d) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
e) Problem solving skills	1	2	3	4	5
9. Based on your experience, is it difficult to assess an individual's soft skills?	NO	YES			
9a) How important is each of the following ways to	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely	3 - Partially	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant

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assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals?		insignificant	significant		
a) Psychological tests	1	2	3	4	5
b) Interviewing	1	2	3	4	5
c) Observation in team activities	1	2	3	4	5
d) Reference checks	1	2	3	4	5
e) Detailed observation of communication and behavior	1	2	3	4	5

THANK YOU!

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Table 3a. Verifying the options that will be part of the Questionnaire for experts (Table 3)

	1					2a					3					4					5.1					5.2					6					7					8					9a								
	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e				
E1	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	5	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	5	4	4	4	5	5	3	3	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	3	2	4	4	5	4	5	4							
E2	5	4	5	4	3	5	5	4	3	5	5	4	4	4	3	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	3	3	5	3	4	3	4	4	5	3	5	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	3	4	4	3	5						
E3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	3	4	3	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	3	5						
E4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	2	3	3	4	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	5	4	4	5	4	4	4							
E5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	3	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5							
E6	5	4	5	3	2	5	5	2	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	5	3	3	5	5	5	3	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5							
E7	4	5	5	2	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	4	3	5	5	5	2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	3	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5								
E8	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5							
E9	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	3	4	5	5	5						
E10	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	5	5	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	4						
E11	5	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	3	5	5	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	5	4	3	3	3	2	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	2	4	4	5				
E12	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	3	4	5	5	4	3	4	5	5	5	4	3	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	5	3	5	5					
E13	4	4	5	3	3	5	5	5	3	3	4	5	3	4	5	4	3	3	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1	3	4	5	5	5	3	3	5	5	3	5	5	5	3	4	3	5	5	4	3	3	5	5	5				
E14	5	5	4	3	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	3	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	3	3	4	4	4	3	5	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	5	
E15	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	3	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	3	5	4	5	5			
E16	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	5	3	4	4	3	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	3	5	5	5			
E17	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	3	4	4			
E18	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	4	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	4	5	4	
E19	4	4	5	3	3	5	5	5	3	3	4	5	3	4	5	4	3	3	5	5	5	4	3	3	3	1	3	4	5	5	5	3	3	5	5	3	5	5	5	3	4	3	5	5	4	3	3	5	5	5	5			
E20	5	5	4	3	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	3	4	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	3	3	4	4	4	3	5	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	5
Total	18	17	18	14	11	18	18	15	12	17	18	17	12	16	14	16	15	17	17	15	18	17	12	14	10	10	16	14	18	16	18	13	16	16	15	13	15	15	16	15	16	13	15	15	17	11	15	17	13	17				
Relative	1	0,9	1	0,7	0,6	1	1	0,8	0,6	0,9	1	0,9	0,7	0,8	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,9	0,8	1	0,9	0,6	0,7	0,5	0,5	0,8	0,7	1	0,8	1	0,7	0,9	0,9	0,8	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,8	0,9	0,7	0,8	0,8	1	0,6	0,8	1	0,7	1				
Higer than 0.7 stays in questionaire	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y				

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The data collected in the second round are statistically processed. If more than 70% of the experts rated the offered answer as significant or very significant, it is considered that a consensus has been reached. The calculation is presented in Table 3a.

Then, that skill/reason for development/how to build and strengthen/prerequisite (by question) qualifies to go into the quantitative questionnaire. This Questionnaire is the basis of empirical research on a sample of at least 100 units (in all 4 countries), in order to identify the needs of organizations in these countries when it comes to "soft" skills.

4. Needs analysis questionnaire

Based on the relative score, calculated in the Table 3, the decision has been made on options that do not deserve to have place in the final questionnaire, which will be used for Needs analysis. The modifications are needed for questions 1, 2a, 3, 5.1, 5.2 and 9a.

Question	Answer				
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Teamwork skills	1	2	3	4	5
c) Adaptability	1	2	3	4	5
d) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
1a) Is it possible to ignore soft skills in modern business conditions?	NO	YES			
2. Is the presence of soft skills more important than hard skills for some jobs?	NO	YES			
2a) If yes, how significant is it for the following jobs?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Human resources	1	2	3	4	5
b) Leadership and management	1	2	3	4	5
c) Customer service	1	2	3	4	5
d) CEO	1	2	3	4	5
3. How important are the following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Adaptability and flexibility	1	2	3	4	5
c) Team work and cooperation	1	2	3	4	5
d) Critical thinking	1	2	3	4	5

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4. How important are the following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Building strong relationships	1	2	3	4	5
b) Contribution to teamwork	1	2	3	4	5
c) Motivating staff	1	2	3	4	5
d) Opportunity for personal development	1	2	3	4	5
e) Resolving conflicts	1	2	3	4	5
5) According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system, and in which of the following ways in the workplace, soft skills building and strengthening activities should be approached?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
5.1) In the education system:					
a) Encourage group projects	1	2	3	4	5
b) Special courses and training programs	1	2	3	4	5
c) Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs	1	2	3	4	5
5.2) In the workplace:					
a) Special courses and training programs	1	2	3	4	5
b) Mentoring one-on-one or in groups	1	2	3	4	5
c) Active communication with employees	1	2	3	4	5
d) Being receptive to feedback	1	2	3	4	5
6. How important are the following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Openness to learning	1	2	3	4	5
b) Empathy	1	2	3	4	5
c) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
d) Adaptability	1	2	3	4	5
e) Self-awareness	1	2	3	4	5
7. To what extent are the	1 -	2 -	3 -	4 -	5 - Very

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following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business?	Unnecessary	Completely insignificant	Partially significant	Significant	significant
a) Leadership skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
c) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
d) Problem solving skills	1	2	3	4	5
e) Teamwork	1	2	3	4	5
8. To what extent are the following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Communication skills	1	2	3	4	5
b) Team work	1	2	3	4	5
c) Adaptability and flexibility	1	2	3	4	5
d) Emotional intelligence	1	2	3	4	5
e) Problem solving skills	1	2	3	4	5
9. Based on your experience, is it difficult to assess an individual's soft skills?	NO	YES			
9a) How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals?	1 - Unnecessary	2 - Completely insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
b) Interviewing	1	2	3	4	5
c) Observation in team activities	1	2	3	4	5
d) Reference checks	1	2	3	4	5
e) Detailed observation of communication and behavior	1	2	3	4	5

Since the questionnaire for the experts included 10 questions with five options, the fact that 7 options in total are excluded shows great consistency of this expert group, even it is composed from experts from four widening countries. This questionnaire has been used for gathering data under the Needs analysis.

By comparing the results of the Delphi study, focus groups and the needs analysis of organizations, a realistic picture will be created of the importance and need for the development of certain "soft" skills among young people.